

ECONOMIC LEGAL PROCEEDINGS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE MARKET
ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Ibratova Feruza

Professor of Tashkent State Law University, Doctor of Law

Mirzhalolova Nazokat

Student of Tashkent State Law University

ANNOTATION

This article will consider Economic litigation from the point of view of its functioning in the conditions of the market economy of Uzbekistan. The article highlights the features and main directions of development of the judicial system, regulation of economic disputes, as well as the role of the economic court in the legal support of the functioning of the market economy. The importance of legal regulation for the stability and development of the national economy is emphasized, analyzed and studied. Effective actions in the judicial system are proposed that allow economic entities to find fair protection.

Keywords: economic litigation, market economy, subjects of economic dispute, judicial system, taxation, global economy.

Economic litigation is an important element of the legal system, especially in the context of transition economies, in particular in developing countries such as Uzbekistan. The transformations taking place in the country's economy with the transition to a market economy required reforming and improving the judicial system to ensure fair resolution of economic disputes¹. In this regard, the question of how economic disputes are regulated in a market economy and how the judicial system responds to challenges associated with changes in the economy becomes important.

With the transition to a market economy in the countries of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, the requirements for legislative regulation of economic relations, as well as for the functioning of the judicial system, which must ensure stability, justice and legal protection in the market, are changing significantly².

The specifics of economic litigation in Uzbekistan are determined by the historical context, the rapid development of market relations in the country, as well as reforms aimed at improving the judiciary and creating a favorable legal climate for doing business³. It is important to note that in a market economy, the need for effective resolution of disputes between business entities becomes especially relevant, since business and financial relations require clear regulation and compliance with legal norms.

The system of economic litigation is a mechanism for resolving disputes arising between participants in market activities, such as companies, entrepreneurs, government agencies, legal entities and

¹ Mustafakulov S. МУЛКИЙ ИСЛОҚОТЛАРГА КЕНГ ЙЎЛ ОЧИБ БЕРИШ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШНИНГ БОШ МЕЗОНИ //Nordic_Press. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 0001.

² Довлатова Г. П. и др. Инновации, тенденции и проблемы в области экономики, управления и бизнеса. – 2021.

³ Ибрatова Ф., Миркамилова М., Каршиева Ф. Значение, роль и сущность медиации в экономических спорах //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 11-17.

citizens, related to commercial, financial and economic activities⁴. The effectiveness of judicial proceedings directly affects the attractiveness of the country to foreign investors, the development of entrepreneurship and ensuring fair competition in the market. It is important that the judiciary be able to effectively protect the economic interests of the parties, while ensuring compliance with international standards and legal norms.

Uzbekistan, being in the stage of active economic reforms, faced the need to modernize the judicial system, adapt legislation to the realities of the market economy. An important milestone on this path was the creation of specialized economic courts, which became an important tool for resolving economic disputes and ensuring legal protection on the economic front⁵. These changes pose new challenges for the judicial system, including improving the qualifications of judges, developing the institution of forensic experts, improving the legislative framework and strengthening the trust of citizens and businesses in the judiciary.

One of the key aspects is the development of legal mechanisms that ensure the protection of both domestic participants in economic activity and foreign investors⁶. In the context of globalization and liberalization of economic relations, Uzbekistan will have to not only adapt its legislation to international standards, but also resolve issues related to the effectiveness of judicial review, enforcement of court decisions and the use of alternative dispute resolution mechanisms. The main objective of this study is to analyze the existing features and problems of economic litigation in Uzbekistan in a market economy, as well as to identify ways to improve judicial practice and the legal framework to increase the effectiveness of resolving economic disputes and protecting the rights of market participants.

Economic litigation in a market economy

Economic litigation covers the consideration of disputes arising between legal entities and individuals in the sphere of business, trade and other economic relations. In a market economy, this process becomes an important tool for protecting the rights of participants in economic relations, ensuring justice and preventing economic crimes⁷. In recent decades, reforms have been carried out in Uzbekistan aimed at developing market relations and improving the legal system. One of the steps aimed at improving legal proceedings in the economic sphere was the establishment of the Economic Court under the Supreme Court in Uzbekistan in 2004. This measure significantly increased the efficiency of consideration of economic disputes, providing a more specialized approach and expertise in matters related to economic relations, property rights, taxation, debts and many other aspects of entrepreneurial activity⁸.

Subsequently, in 2017, a reform was introduced that improved the functioning of the judicial system, strengthened the role of judges in economic law, and increased liability for violating the rights of

⁴ Гулямова Н. Р. ИҚТИСОДИЙ СУДАЛАРДА ДАЛИЛЛАР ТУШУНЧАСИ, УНИНГ ТУРЛАРИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ //Экономика и социум. – 2024. – №. 6-2 (121). – С. 1001-1008.

⁵ Махмудов Х. А. Россия Федерациясида Чет Давлат Суд Ва Арбитраж Ҳал Қилув Қарорларини Тан Олиш Ва Ижрога Қаратиш Тартиби //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2024. – Т. 45. – С. 14-18.

⁶ Ибратова Ф. и др. ПРАВОВЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКАЗАТЕЛЬСТВА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 18-24.

⁷ Давлатов М. Ф. СУДЛАРДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ НИЗОЛАРНИ КЎРИШНИ РАҚАМЛАШТИРИШНИНГ ОДИЛ СУДЛОВГА ЭРИШИШДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ //Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5-1. – С. 180-183.

⁸ Балташева З. А. РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ СУД ЭКСПЕРТИЗА ТИЗИМИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ //Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 105-108.

market participants. The Economic Court has the authority to consider cases related to breach of contractual obligations, bankruptcy, debt obligations, as well as contentious issues in the field of taxation and financial violations. Litigation in the economic sphere plays an important role in maintaining law and order and respecting the rights of market participants. The main functions of economic litigation in Uzbekistan are as follows:

- protection of the rights and interests of market participants. Economic courts protect the rights of business entities, including protection against illegal actions by the state or other market participants. Judicial practice is actively used to resolve disputes related to contracts, debts, violations of antitrust laws and other economic rights⁹.
- stimulating economic growth and attracting investment. Creating a transparent and effective judicial system that protects the rights of businesses, helps attract foreign investors and create a favorable investment climate. Judicial protection of the rights of investors and entrepreneurs is one of the important factors in the stability of a market economy.
- resolution of financial and tax disputes. Economic litigation in Uzbekistan is actively involved in resolving disputes related to taxation, tax arrears, as well as issues related to financial offenses and bankruptcy¹⁰.

Problems and challenges of economic litigation in a market economy

Economic litigation in Uzbekistan, as in other countries with transition economies, faces a number of problems and challenges that affect the efficiency and transparency of resolving economic disputes and the functioning of market relations. In the context of the rapid development of a market economy, reforms in the legal and judicial spheres, the problems and challenges of economic litigation require special attention and a comprehensive approach.

1. ***Insufficient qualifications of judges and specialists in the economic field.*** One of the key problems is the insufficient qualifications of judges and specialists working in the field of economic litigation. Despite the development of specialized courts, many judges do not have sufficient knowledge and experience in the field of economics, finance and business. This can lead to errors in assessing evidence, incorrect application of legislation and unfair decisions.

Solution: To solve this problem, it is necessary to conduct more in-depth training of judges, create advanced training programs that include courses in economics, finance and modern market mechanisms. Another important step is to involve forensic experts and consultants with specialized knowledge in the field of economics.

2. ***Problems with the execution of court decisions.*** One of the serious problems in economic litigation is the insufficient efficiency of the execution of court decisions. Despite the existence of a court decision, problems with its execution may arise due to bureaucratic barriers, poor performance of bailiffs and ineffective coordination between various government agencies. This is especially important for resolving disputes between large economic entities and government agencies, where the execution of a court decision may encounter obstacles.

⁹ Абидов Д. Қонуний кучга кирган суд ҳужжатларини янги очилган ҳолатлар бўйича қайта кўриш бўйича суд амалиёти ва хорижий тажриба: қиёсий-ҳуқуқий таҳлил //Наука, инновации и образование: ключевые векторы общественного прогресса. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 62-70.

¹⁰ Хаитбоев А. О. Тўловга қобилиятсизлик аломатлари ва иқтисодий судга мурожаат қилиш тартиби //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 883-888.

Solution: To improve the efficiency of the execution of court decisions, it is necessary to improve the coordination between judicial bodies and government agencies, strengthen the work of bailiffs, and carry out reforms aimed at improving the legal framework and processes for the execution of decisions.

3. Problems with the rights of foreign investors. Given Uzbekistan's integration into the global economy and the desire to attract foreign investors, the issue of protecting their rights in the judicial system is of particular importance. Foreign investors, when faced with legal disputes, may not have sufficient guarantees of legal protection, which makes investments in the country less attractive.

Solution: To improve the situation, it is necessary to create more reliable mechanisms for protecting the rights of foreign investors, including establishing clearer and more transparent procedures for resolving disputes, improving judicial practice in matters of investment protection and the application of international treaties in the field of investment law.

4. The role of forensic experts and judicial practice. In economic cases, there is often a need for specialized forensic experts, especially in the areas of finance, taxation and business valuation¹¹. However, in Uzbekistan there is a shortage of qualified experts in some areas of the economy, which may affect the quality and objectivity of court decisions.

Solution: Developing the institution of forensic experts, improving their qualifications, and improving interaction between experts and judges can significantly improve the quality of court decisions and help resolve complex economic disputes.

3. Prospects for the development of economic litigation in Uzbekistan

In the context of economic transformation and the desire to integrate with the global economic system, Uzbekistan is faced with the need to improve its legislation and judicial system to ensure more effective resolution of economic disputes and protection of the rights of business entities. For the further development of economic litigation in Uzbekistan, measures are needed to improve legal regulation, strengthen trust in the judicial system and expand legal mechanisms for protecting business interests. In particular, it is important to continue developing alternative dispute resolution institutions, including arbitration, which will speed up the process of resolving economic disputes¹². It is also worth noting that the legal system must take into account the dynamically changing conditions of the global economy, which will require a more flexible adaptation of judicial practice and legislation.

One of the key factors determining the effectiveness of economic litigation is the presence of a developed and flexible legal framework that would meet the requirements of a market economy and international standards.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been actively implementing legislative reforms aimed at improving the business climate and strengthening the rule of law¹³. However, due to the dynamic development of the economy and international integration, legislation requires constant updating. Uzbekistan's experience shows that it is necessary to continue modernizing work in the field of commercial and

¹¹ Babakulovna I. F. Peculiarities of consideration of cases related to inheritance in civil courts in the Republic of Uzbekistan. – 2023.

¹² Ибратова Ф. Правовые вопросы медиация как альтернативный способ урегулирования споров //Слияние экономических и правовых идей: перспективы для инновационного роста. – 2023. – С. 5-14.

¹³ Расулев Д. ЭКОНОМИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА И СТРАН СНГ: ЦИФРЫ И КОММЕНТАРИИ //Архив научных исследований. – 2020. – Т. 34.

investment law. This will strengthen legal guarantees for foreign investors and increase the level of protection of business rights.

It is important to focus on the development and implementation of specialized norms that will cover new areas of the economy, such as the digital economy, financial technologies, ecology and sustainable development, which will allow for effective dispute resolution in these rapidly developing areas. Economic cases require specific knowledge in areas such as business practices, taxation, financial transactions, and often the lack of such knowledge among judges can lead to errors in decision-making. In order to avoid such problems, an important step in the future will be the creation of permanent educational programs for judges, including courses in economics, financial law, and international standards. It is also necessary to develop a system of professional certification for judges working in the economic sphere¹⁴.

Modern information technologies can also significantly increase the efficiency and transparency of judicial proceedings. The introduction of electronic technologies into the system of economic legal proceedings will speed up the consideration of cases; make the processes more accessible and transparent for the parties and society as a whole. The creation and development of platforms for filing claims, interacting with the courts, and holding court hearings online can significantly increase the speed and accessibility of justice. The development and implementation of electronic systems for the automation of the processes of filing and considering cases, exchanging information between courts and other government agencies will reduce the bureaucratic burden and increase the efficiency of the courts.

The prospects for the development of economic litigation in Uzbekistan directly depend on the further improvement of the judicial system, the legal framework and the introduction of modern technologies. It is important that Uzbekistan continues to reform the judicial system in accordance with the best international practices, thus creating conditions for the effective resolution of economic disputes, increasing the level of trust in the judiciary and ensuring legal security for business. Careful work on these aspects will contribute to the sustainable development of the economy, attracting investment and strengthening market relations in the country.

List of references

1. Mustafakulov S. МУЛКИЙ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРГА КЕНГ ЙЎЛ ОЧИБ БЕРИШ-ИҚТИСОДИЙ РИВОЖЛАНИШНИНГ БОШ МЕЗОНИ //Nordic_Press. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 0001.
2. Довлатова Г. П. и др. Инновации, тенденции и проблемы в области экономики, управления и бизнеса. – 2021.
3. Ибратова Ф., Миркамилова М., Каршиева Ф. Значение, роль и сущность медиации в экономических спорах //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 11-17.
4. Гулямова Н. Р. ИҚТИСОДИЙ СУДАЛАРДА ДАЛИЛЛАР ТУШУНЧАСИ, УНИНГ ТУРЛАРИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ //Экономика и социум. – 2024. – №. 6-2 (121). – С. 1001-1008.
5. Махмудов Х. А. Россия Федерациясида Чет Давлат Суд Ва Арбитраж Ҳал Қилув Қарорларини Тан Олиш Ва Ижрога Қаратиш Тартиби //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2024. – Т. 45. – С. 14-18.

¹⁴ Захаров В. В. Специализация судей как средство совершенствования правосудия //Российский судья. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 31-36.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

6. Ибратова Ф. и др. ПРАВОВЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКАЗАТЕЛЬСТВА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ //International journal of professional science. – 2022. – №. 4. – С. 18-24.
7. Давлатов М. Ф. СУДЛАРДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ НИЗОЛАРНИ КЎРИШНИ РАҚАМЛАШТИРИШНИНГ ОДИЛ СУДЛОВГА ЭРИШИШДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ //Central Asian Journal of Education and Innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5-1. – С. 180-183.
8. Балташева З. А. РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТДА ИҚТИСОДИЙ СУД ЭКСПЕРТИЗА ТИЗИМИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ //Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 105-108.
9. Абидов Д. Қонуний кучга кирган суд хужжатларини янги очилган ҳолатлар бўйича қайта кўриш бўйича суд амалиёти ва хорижий тажриба: қиёсий-ҳуқуқий таҳлил //Наука, инновации и образование: ключевые векторы общественного прогресса. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 62-70.
10. Хаитбоев А. О. Тўловга қобилятсизлик аломатлари ва иқтисодий судга мурожаат қилиш тартиби //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 883-888.
11. Babakulovna I. F. Peculiarities of consideration of cases related to inheritance in civil courts in the Republic of Uzbekistan. – 2023.
12. Ибратова Ф. Правовые вопросы медиация как альтернативный способ урегулирования споров //Слияние экономических и правовых идей: перспективы для инновационного роста. – 2023. – С. 5-14.
13. Расулев Д. ЭКОНОМИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА И СТРАН СНГ: ЦИФРЫ И КОММЕНТАРИИ //Архив научных исследований. – 2020. – Т. 34.
14. Захаров В. В. Специализация судей как средство совершенствования правосудия //Российский судья. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 31-36.